

A Preliminary Exploration Of The Social Value Made By Chinese Female Pianists In The Democratic Revolution Movement In The First Half Of The 20th Century

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: December 02, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Chinese Female Pianist, Democratic Revolutionary Movement, Social Value</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7391497</p>	<p><i>This paper adopts the method of literature research and content analysis, and takes Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century as the research object who dedicates themselves to the country and the party through direct participation in the democratic revolutionary movement and indirect investment. To explore their social value in the democratic revolutionary movement. That is to say, in the democratic revolutionary movement in the first half of the 20th century, Chinese female pianists, as one of the forces among the intellectuals, played a leading and exemplary role for the vast number of people of insight with their ardent patriotism. In another way, these female pianists participate the democratic revolution in ways including a direct participation, economic support, carrying out active propaganda and organizational activities through the weapon of music and awakening countless people with lofty ideals. They have played a positive role in realizing the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation as well as displaying their life value and social value. The current research on this subject with its value as being rare both at home and abroad, can be said to fill the gap in the research of Chinese female pianists and democratic revolutionary movements in the first half of the 20th century and makes a significant sense in reality as well as practical value, especially for the interdisciplinary research between sociology and musicology today. The ultimate goal is to let the younger generations understand the revolutionary feelings of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century with roles of being a human, teacher, making a study and hopefully they will inspire Chinese female pianists in the 21st century to create brilliance on the road of piano art in the future.</i></p>

Introduction

The first half of the 20th century is characterized with the surging democratic revolutionary movements including the most historically significant Xinhai Revolution (1911), May Fourth Movement (1919), the National Revolution (1924-1927); Agrarian Revolution (1927-1937); Sino-Japanese War (1931-1945) and Liberation War (1946-1950). Among them, the Xinhai Revolution was a relatively complete Chinese bourgeois democratic revolution launched by progressive intellectuals at that time, which finally overthrew the Qing government and ended the rule of China's feudal dynasty that has lasted for more than 2,000 years; The May Fourth Movement was a thoroughly anti-imperialist and anti-feudal democratic revolutionary movement initiated and organized by a broader and more conscious intellectual, which laid the foundation for the birth of the Communist Party of China and brought China's anti-imperialist and anti-feudal bourgeois democratic revolution to an unprecedented historical stage; During the period of the national revolution, a large number of revolutionary intellectuals directly participated in the workers' and peasants' struggles emerged, and many revolutionary songs of workers and peasants with proletarian revolutionary ideological content were composed, which directly met the needs of the revolutionary struggle; During the period of the Agrarian Revolution, revolutionary literary and artistic groups composed of intellectuals carried out revolutionary musical activities in the base areas and composed many revolutionary folk songs and songs of the workers' and peasants' Red Army that reflected the new life of freedom and happiness for the people in the revolutionary base areas, which played a great role in agitating the political struggle at that time and also had a far-reaching impact on the development of music in different periods later. During the Anti-Japanese War period, a large number of intellectuals and music workers united under the banner of anti-Japanese salvation, took up the weapon of music, and actively participated in the front line of anti-Japanese propaganda against Japan Appeal to the destruction of Chinese education by the Japanese army and win the support of people around the world; In the Liberated Areas under the leadership of the Communist Party during the War of Liberation, with Yan'an as the center of the revolutionary base area, intellectuals and literary and art workers took advantage of the appeal of music and the

momentum of thousands of troops to carry out vigorous mass singing activities, thus making due contributions to promoting the development process of China's democratic revolutionary movement.

Throughout these unprecedented revolutionary movements, intellectuals have shown a high degree of consciousness in ways of walking in the forefront of the revolutionary ranks, and playing a leading and exemplary role for the vast number of people of insight, while Chinese female pianists, as one of the forces among intellectuals, have not been outdone in successive democratic revolutionary movements, with their fervent patriotism, or Directly participating in the democratic revolutionary movement, or indirectly using economic support, or leading by example, using music education as a weapon, and using music as a weapon of battle, carried out active propaganda and organization activities, awakened countless people with lofty ideals to participate in the democratic revolutionary movement, and played their due positive role in realizing the Chinese dream of the great rejuvenation of the Chinese nation, reflecting them Life value and social value.

Perhaps it is because of the innermost call of the same female pianist, or perhaps because of the piano, which changed the fate of her life, the research of Chinese female pianists has always been the focus of the research. And the reason why the development of Chinese piano art has its followers; The reason why the "piano fever" continues to heat up; The reason why China's piano art achievements are brilliant now is inseparable from the artistic charm, artistic appeal and artistic influence of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century. As the "half of the sky" of pianists of the same period, Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century made indispensable contributions to the development history of Chinese piano art, which provokes the motive to write the article.

The research on the female pianists during the first half of the 20th century is comparatively rare touched both at home and abroad. and it can be said that it fills the gap in the research of Chinese female pianists and democratic revolutionary movements in the first half of the 20th century, and has made a profound significance to the reality and practical value, especially for the interdisciplinary research between sociology and musicology today. The ultimate goal is to let the younger generations understand the revolutionary feelings of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century as people, teachers, learning, patriotism, dedication and selfless dedication, and inspire Chinese female pianists in the 21st century to create brilliance on the road of piano art in the future.

Based on the innovation and goals of the above research, this paper takes Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century as the research object. Based on related collection of literature, more than 90 female pianists are within the range of the research. Research questions for this paper are as follows: (1) the social value of Chinese female pianists in the democratic revolution movement in the first half of the 20th century. Based on the outstanding performance of the 90 female pianists in the democratic revolution movement in different periods, six representative female pianists are chosen as the specific research objects: Shi Fengzhu, Wang Ruixian, Li Cuizhen, Li Xianmin, Zhiming, and Zhou Guangren are discussed in this article, and the article adopts the method of literature research and content analysis. Analyze them one by one.

Theoretical basis and literature review

2.1 Theoretical basis

Feminist music research began around the 70s of the 20th century, under the influence of the feminist movement and feminist academic thought, it was set off in the American musicology community. The original intention was "to address the oblivion of the place of women musicians in the European tradition, to enable their works to be published, recorded and to study their place in music history". Representative scholars include Susan McClary (1946—), Marcia J. Citron (1945—), and Ruth Solie (1946—), Suzanne Cusick, et al. Their critical writings have led to the gradual development of feminist music studies into one of the main aspects of critical musicology.

This paper analyzes several representative situations of Chinese female pianists' participation in the democratic revolution movement in the first half of the 20th century from the perspective of anthropology-influenced, one of the approaches to the study of feminist music, namely anthropology-influenced. In the field of musicology, music can be understood as an aspect of culture, mainly studying the interrelationship between music history and social history, so the issue of women as research objects is particularly important. In addition, if the study of music performance is emphasized, then the feminist point of view, women and the efforts of women involved in this discipline will be closely related. Moreover, if we can dig deeper into the two fields of women and music, we may be surprised to find that we have completely ignored that in the study of many aspects of music history, in fact, female musicians are involved, very active, and have outstanding results.

Current women's musicological research is mainly due to the study of women's history done by women historians. According to women historians, women are not only influenced by their environment, but they also contribute to the development of this environment; There are women actively involved in every moment and every aspect of history, and if women's activities are included, the contours of history will change significantly.

2.2 Literature review

According to the above theoretical basis and guiding ideology, this paper adopts the method of literature research and content analysis to collect and organize the relevant data of six representatives of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century: "Biography of Chinese Modern and Modern Musicians" edited by the Music Research Institute of the Chinese Academy of Arts and edited by Xiang Yansheng (1994), in Volume 2, Zhu Ping's "Hope for Tomorrow - Female Composers Send Ming", The pianist Zhu Ming gave a brief description of the concrete expression of his firm conviction to devote himself to the revolutionary cause in his youth. In particular, the account of her abandoning the favorable urban living conditions, traveling thousands of miles, rushing to the forefront of the revolutionary struggle, and using the unique appeal of music to carry out active revolutionary propaganda activities sparked the author's idea of writing this article.

Bian Meng is mentioned in her book *The Formation and Development of Chinese Piano Culture* (1996), "Early Chinese Piano Professional Performance and Teaching Activities" to Shi Fengzhu, and made a brief account of Shi Fengzhu's performance and teaching in a footnote; Gong Hongyu's thesis "An unexpected encounter with Shi Fengzhu, a teacher at Huang Zi Tsinghua School" (2019), introduces Shi Fengzhu's situation in different periods, including: birth environment, study experience, piano learning performance, teaching achievements, etc. In particular, Shi Fengzhu actively participated in progressive social activities during her stay in Shanghai and was a sponsor of the Chinese feminist and revolutionary movements.

Feng Xiaogang's doctoral dissertation "Chinese Piano Music Culture in the First Half of the 20th Century" (2007), one of the cradles of Chinese pianists, has a special account of Wang Ruixian in the introduction of the arduous and entrepreneurial stage of piano education at the National Shanghai Conservatory of Music, and has been to the United States twice to specialize in piano performance, National Shanghai Conservatory of Music served as the piano team leader until he left Shangyin and founded the Children's Music Academy, committed to cultivating a generation of young pianists.

Feng Wenzhong also gave a brief introduction to Li Cuizhen's life and deeds, especially praising her intelligent talent and high performance talent; In Volume 2, Chao Zhijue wrote "Born in Si Born in Si Died in Si - Female Piano Educator Li Cuizhen", introduced Li Cuizhen's extraordinary talent, superhuman diligence, persistent pursuit, self-humble spirit, self-reliance and self-improvement tendencies, rigorous and standardized performance style and teaching style. She was a representative of an intellectual of that era who did not want to be a slave to the state, was full of patriotic fervor, cleansed herself, and had a sense of justice.

Kered published "Piano Teaching in China's Past and Present: An Interview with Pianist Li Xianmin" (1984) and Ouyang Meilun's "Li Xianmin Talks." 1989 Trip to China" (1991) is an account of two interviews with Mr. Li Xianmin at different times It recorded what Mr. Li Xianmin saw and heard when he returned to China and her deep feelings about the changes and development of piano music education in the motherland in different periods; Feng Wenzhong said that Li Xianmin was the first female pianist to promote Chinese piano music overseas, and her high achievements, great contributions and profound influence have made indispensable contributions to the history of the development of Chinese piano art; Liao Fushu's "Mourning Old Alumnus Li Xianmin" (1992) was published when the author heard the Shanghai music on the other side of the Pacific Ocean After the death of Mr. Li Xianmin, an old alumnus of a bachelor's degree, he used the method of reminiscence to record Mr. Li's deeds of his motherland despite being abroad, including his name, clothing and frequent performance of Chinese works.

In the fourth volume of Xiang's book, Zhao Shimin wrote "The Piano is My Life - Female Pianist Zhou Guangren", and his life credo to Mr. Zhou: The piano is my life, from the growth environment, study experience, from the teacher to learn the piano, performance honors, teaching achievements, and insistence on staying in China, cultivating talents for the motherland, etc., made a more detailed demonstration; Huang Dagang edited "Zhou Guangren Piano Teaching Art" (2006), which is Mr. Zhou Guangren's experience of more than 60 years of teaching, comprehensive and systematic, which is an academic work describing Mr. Zhou's piano teaching ideas and artistic concepts. It is worth learning from every music professional and enthusiast who loves piano art, engaged in piano performance and teaching; Pufang published "Ling Han Hongmei Welcomes the Spring Breeze - Remembering the Famous Pianist and Educator Zhou Guangren" (2022), to Mr. Zhou He made a detailed and comprehensive summary of his life, giving Mr. Zhou high praise and praise.

From the above literature, it can be seen that although the academic circles have achieved a lot of research on Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century, there are still some shortcomings and areas to be studied in depth. In fact, in the long river of development of Chinese piano art, Chinese female pianists played an important role in the first half of the 20th century. The history of music in this period seems to have been concluded, but the current research on music history at home and abroad is mostly considered from the perspective of men, and on the whole, it can be said to be a bit one-sided. Especially for the study of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century, historians generally did not pay much and comprehensive attention to it, or even ignored it. For example, there is little research on the teaching characteristics of Chinese female pianists in the first half of the 20th century, and there is a lack of research on the participation and

influence of Chinese female pianists in the democratic revolutionary movement of the same period in the first half of the 20th century.

Results & Analysis

Through the sorting and classification of collected data, the specific representative situation of Chinese female pianists participating in the democratic revolutionary movement in the first half of the 20th century is analyzed as follows:

3.1 Directly invested in the representatives involved in the democratic revolutionary movement: Zhiming

Zhi Ming was an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists who directly participated in the democratic revolutionary movement before and after the Second Sino-Japanese War. During the War of Resistance Against Japanese Aggression, the Chinese people in the occupied areas lived in dire straits, and the country was facing difficulties, and the vast number of patriotic musicians resolutely walked out of the classroom, some rushed to the anti-Japanese battlefield, and some went deep behind enemy lines or in the liberated areas to carry out anti-Japanese literary and artistic propaganda activities. Therefore, the creation of Chinese vocal works that conform to mass collective music activities has become the main direction of the development of Chinese music culture during this period, while the development of the piano profession has been greatly restricted and affected.

Pinning on Ming, that is, "pinning hopes on tomorrow", expressed her firm belief in devoting herself to the revolutionary cause after arriving in Yan'an. Formerly known as Wu Yazhen, he used the name Wu Ziping. Born in Suzhou on June 29, 1917, he was admitted to the Chinese Music Group of Shanghai National College of Music High School in 1933, with a minor subject of piano. In 1935, he switched to piano major, studied under Russian piano professor Lazareff, and graduated in the summer of 1937 at the age of 20, with a revolutionary dream. Leave the warm family, undergo training and testing in the torrent of national liberation, and go to find your own combat post. Everywhere she went, in addition to serving as a music teacher at school, she also actively participated in anti-Japanese singing activities. Using music as a weapon of battle to participate in the local democratic revolutionary movement, she later went to Yan'an, the holy place of revolution, to start a new stage in her life. She was the first pianist in the Yan'an era, and during Lu Yi's teaching, what she learned was more useful, that is, to serve the people of the new era. After joining the Communist Party of China, she never forgot to fight for the liberation of women, during which she participated in the Yan'an Literary and Art Forum, the Rectification Movement, and the Qingge Movement presided over by Comrade Mao Zedong; He has worked in the Music Department of the College of Arts and Literature of North China Union University, the Music Department of Lu Xun College of Literature and Art of Northeastern University, Mudanjiang Luyi Art Troupe, Northeast Music Work Group, Northeast Music Troupe Junior Class, Northeast Music College, Music Department of the Film Bureau of the Central Ministry of Culture, Music Creation Studio of Shanghai Film Studio and other places. In the later period, he mainly followed the situation to create various musical works. The children's songs "Youth, Youth, Spring of the Motherland" (lyrics by Li Yourong) and "We Are the Successors of Communism" (lyrics by Zhou Yuhui) composed by Zhi Ming represent the outstanding achievements of Chinese children's songwriting. With her practical actions, Zhi Ming wrote a new chapter in the democratic revolution movement of a Chinese female pianist, which is worthy of future generations.

3.2 Indirectly investing in and participating in the democratic revolutionary movement

3.2.1 Representatives with financial support: Shi Fengzhu, Wang Ruixian

3.2.1.1 Shi Fengzhu

Shi Fengzhu is an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists who financially supported the democratic revolutionary movement before and after the Xinhai Revolution. From the beginning of the 20th century to before and after the Xinhai Revolution, with the rise of new schools, pianos were widely used in the activities of school music and gradually expanded to society, so as to truly participate in the lives of Chinese people. During this period, piano music also entered some civilian families, so Chinese students had the opportunity to learn to play the piano. From the Italian pianist Mario Paci (1878-1946) who first held piano recitals and engaged in piano teaching in Shanghai, to more foreign pianists settled in China to promote the development of piano art. The vigorous development of China's new music culture in modern times has laid a good foundation.

Shi Fengzhu, born in Kunshan, Jiangsu Province, graduated from Shanghai Zhongxi Girls' School in 1905, went to the United States to study in 1907, obtained a bachelor's degree in music in 1910, returned to China in August of the same year, and worked as a music teacher at the Shanghai Church School Yan Mo's Girls' School in 1911. From 1912 to 1918, she taught piano at her alma mater, Shanghai Jungxi Women's School, and in February 1913, she was appointed head of the music department of the Jungxi Women's School.

In 1918, the "Shanghai New News" published that on the evening of May 17, Shi Fengzhu and Cao Shuzhen and Xia Ruth, two students of the Chinese and Western Women's School, held a unique and wonderful piano graduation concert in front of many audiences with musical literacy. Let Westerners know that Chinese girls have extraordinary technical abilities and can play piano pieces with considerable difficulty, far exceeding

the level of Western girls of the same age. Shi Fengzhu served as the second piano and Ruth Xia jointly performed Liszt's "Rhapsody" Opus No. 2, which was unanimously praised by everyone. It shows that Shi Fengzhu has made outstanding contributions to piano music teaching.

Shi Fengzhu is one of the first Chinese female musicians to study music in the United States, the first Chinese student to enter the Juilliard School to study piano, and the first Chinese student to hold a solo concert in the United States, during which she also actively participated in the art activities of American women and local associations. After returning to Japan, she was influenced by her sister, who was keen on social activities, and actively participated in progressive social activities. From Mr. Han Han's research (which year? 引用的年代) on the writings of musicians studying in the United States in the early 20th century, there are records that the sisters Shi Fengbao and Shi Fengzhu "were not only celebrities in Shanghai's cultural circles at that time, but also sponsors of the Chinese feminist movement and revolutionary movement". This can be confirmed by the newspapers in Shanghai at that time. For example, starting from December 3, 1911, the Minli newspaper published the activities of the "Republic of China Women's Music Assistance Association" for five consecutive days: the rise and fall of the family and the country, the responsibility of the husband, and the prosperity of women ... The wise give advice, the brave obey, and the rich help, which leads to the happiness of freedom in the southeast. ... Ms. Shi Fengzhu, a doctor of music in the United States, plays the piano... Admission tickets are sold for one foreign dollar each, and the proceeds are all used for the military....

3.2.1.2 Wang Ruixian

Wang Ruixian was an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists participating in the democratic revolution movement before and after the May Fourth Movement. The outbreak of the May Fourth New Cultural Movement in 1919 greatly promoted the upsurge of Chinese cultural circles to explore new ideas and new knowledge, and heralded the establishment and development of new music culture in modern times. Therefore, under the active initiative of Cai Yuanpei and others, Peking University took the lead in establishing two music societies, such as the Peking University Music Research Association (1919). Subsequently, school music education sprang up like mushrooms, and opened the precedent of higher professional piano education in China, such as the music department of Shanghai Normal College (1920). Under their leadership, many comprehensive universities and church schools across the country have also set up special music departments or departments, which has laid the foundation for promoting the vigorous development of Chinese piano art.

Wang Ruixian, graduated from Shanghai Chinese and Western Women's High School in the early days, is the earliest female pianist in China to study in the United States since May Fourth, and went to the United States twice to study in 1914 and 1919, and obtained a master's degree in piano performance from the New England Conservatory of Music and Wesley College respectively, becoming a Chinese pianist with a double master's degree. After returning to China, in 1927, she was hired by Xiao Youmei as the piano leader of the National Shanghai Conservatory of Music, specializing in piano courses. It is enough to show that Wang Ruixian's piano performance level at that time was very high. In the 30s of the 20th century, due to various reasons, Wang Ruixian had no choice but to leave Shangyin. In the 40s, she founded the Children's Music Academy in Shanghai, focusing on training the younger generation to learn piano, she personally taught, so far, her music school has become one of the cradles of piano music education in Shanghai, and has trained many outstanding piano players and piano music educators. At the same time, they help some children whose families are in difficulty but have great musical talents, and give or waive tuition fees, or provide piano rooms, or living allowances.

After moving to the United States in 1947, she still cares about the piano education of Chinese students studying in the United States, helps in piano learning and life, and cultivates many well-known Chinese pianists overseas. Her piano teaching activities continued until her death in 1973. In line with patriotic enthusiasm and the influence of the progressive intellectuals participating in the revolution at that time, Wang Ruixian returned to her homeland several times to serve the development of piano art in the motherland. At the same time, she used the actions of "the rise and fall of the family and the country, and the responsibility of the man" and "the rich help the salary" to do her best for the democratic revolutionary movement at that time.

3.2.2 Representatives who dedicate themselves to the country and the party in the form of music education: Li Cuizhen, Zhou Guangren

3.2.2.1 Li Cuizhen

Li Cuizhen is an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists who indirectly participated in the democratic revolution movement through music education before and after the National Revolutionary Movement. In this day when the warlords and warring countries were ruined, the three music education institutions in Beijing led by Xiao Youmei were forced to close, but in Shanghai, patriots led by Feng Zikai and other three people successively established the Music Department of Shanghai University of the Arts (1925). On November 27, 1927, with the active support of Cai Yuanpei, Xiao Youmei founded the National Shanghai Conservatory of Music, which was the first independent music academy in China, laying a solid foundation for the future development of Chinese piano art.

Li Cuizhen, born on December 15, 1910 in Shanghai, is a famous pianist and piano educator, a second-level professor at the Shanghai Conservatory of Music, and the first head of the piano department. Li Cuizhen began to learn piano at the age of 5, because of her extraordinary talent, superhuman diligence and persistent pursuit of music, so that when she broke through the Shanghai National College of Music, the level and depth of the level surprised the examiners, and no one among the students dared to ask. One year after entering the school, the 20-year-old Li Cuizhen graduated with full marks and became a curiosity in the Shanghai music industry, and was subsequently known as one of the outstanding representatives of the "Shanghai Piano School", a "piano wizard" and "a talented girl" in the Shanghai music industry.

Although Li Cuizhen was already full of halos when she was young, her self-humility and self-reliance led her to go to the Royal College of Music alone to major in piano and other music courses. In line with the promise of "being born, doing, and dying in Si," and with the patriotic spirit rooted in China, as an intellectual with a sense of justice, in her words, "returning to China is worthy of the motherland." Li Cuizhen gave up the superior living environment and conditions abroad several times, and was willing to devote all her energy and love for the piano to the music education of the motherland, so she resolutely returned to the motherland in August 1940, dedicated to piano teaching. Her rigorous and standardized playing style and teaching style have won high prestige in the music industry and cultivated many outstanding talents for the cause of piano education in New China. Li Cuizhen was a representative of the intellectuals of that era who did not want to be a slave to the state, full of patriotic fervor, clean and self-sufficient, and had a sense of justice, under her influence, many students actively participated in social revolutionary activities in the form of music, and after graduation, they devoted themselves to the revolutionary movement at that time. It played an important role in the victory of the national revolutionary movement.

3.2.2.2 Zhou Guangren

Zhou Guangren was an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists before and after the Liberation War who dedicated themselves to the country and the party through music education. At that time, the music department of the Lu Xun Art Institute, established under the leadership of the Communist Party in Yan'an, successively trained a large number of musicians who met the requirements of the times, and mobilized countless people of insight to actively participate in China's democratic revolution movement in the form of mass singing activities. During this period, China's piano art had a new development trend, and pianists went abroad for further study or returned to China after completing their studies, among which female pianists were: Wu Leyi (studying in France), Li Cuizhen (returning to England) and so on. At the same time, Shanghai National Music has specially cultivated many outstanding piano talents throughout the country, becoming the main force for the development of China's early piano art.

Zhou Guangren, tenured professor of the Central Conservatory of Music, is the most influential and authoritative Chinese pianist, educator and music activist in the international music scene in the 20th century, one of the most outstanding women in the Chinese music industry, and China's piano master. Her ancestral home is Ningbo, Zhejiang Province, and she was born on December 17, 1928 in Hanover, Germany. Influenced by his mother, she has been extremely sensitive to music since she was a child, and began to learn piano at the age of 9, successively studying under Qian Qi, Ding Shande, Yang Jiaren (staying in the United States), and May Pachi (Italy). "The piano is my life", in line with the love and dedication to the piano, Mr. Zhou Guangren has created many firsts in the Chinese piano industry: the first pianist in China to win awards internationally, the first musician to introduce Chinese piano works to the American system, the first Chinese pianist to hold a concert after the "Cultural Revolution", founded the first youth piano school in China, the first piano educator who advocated the popularization of piano education in China, and participated in the formulation of the first "Four-year Undergraduate Piano of the Piano Department of the Central Conservatory of Music" Professional Course Teaching Syllabus", created a precedent for "double piano" to perform on the Chinese stage, edited China's first professional journal of piano art "Piano Art", took the initiative to undertake the establishment of the China International Piano Competition, participated in the first large-scale foreign cultural exchange and performance activity after the founding of New China, and published the most articles among Chinese contemporary pianists.

Mr. Zhou Guangren is widely known among Chinese pianists. She has been using her skilled German and English skills to serve as a translator in major Chinese foreign cultural exchanges, performances and teaching activities, fully demonstrating her communication skills in foreign exchanges, and laying a good foundation for her to enter the world music stage in the future. At the same time, after accumulating rich experience in piano art theory research, performance, teaching and competitions. Mr. Zhou Guangren's performances and lectures have spread all over the country and the world, and she is well received and loved by people everywhere she goes, which shows her solid performance ability and teaching level, and she introduces China's excellent piano works to foreign countries, so that foreign friends can understand Chinese piano music and show the charm of Chinese piano music; She has served as a judge of domestic and international piano competitions dozens of times; Arranged and composed more than 10 piano songs; Organized the compilation of amateur piano examination textbooks, and personally served as the director of the expert review committee of the China Music

Association and the Central Conservatory of Music; The popularization and professional teaching lectures of piano music have been carried out in many publicity windows such as Beijing Concert Hall, CCTV and China Radio and Television University, which has played a leading role in the popularization, promotion and improvement of Chinese piano art.

As a famous professor of the piano department of the Central Conservatory of Music, Mr. Zhou has trained dozens of domestic old, middle and young generations of pianists and educators, and has let her guide and teach countless students; As the head of the piano department of the Central Conservatory of Music, Mr. Zhou has initiated and presided over many important academic conferences, including: "National Piano Music Creation", "Nationalization of Chinese Piano Music", "Main Subject Teaching" and "National Music College Piano Main Teaching Seminar". In addition, she publishes books, writes papers, writes reviews and exchanges for journals, recommends teaching materials, and prefaces to essays for peers and young students, etc., all within the scope of her work, and she has done a very good job.

Mr. Zhou loves and cares for students, regards students as the continuation of her life and career, and with motherly love, cares for students' growth and attention to students' piano learning conditions, she has successively founded "Xinghai Youth Piano School", "Leyou Piano School", "Zhou Guangren Piano Art Center" in many large and small cities across the country, and has lasted since 1996 for 10 years. The "National Piano Teacher Training Course" has led China's "piano fever" and made it continue to heat up, making great contributions to cultivating generations of piano teachers and piano students in China. Mr. Zhou's outstanding contributions and achievements have won her wide acclaim: "National May Day Labor Medal" (1993), "Central Conservatory of Music Outstanding Contribution Award", "Golden Bell Award Lifetime Achievement Award", "Who's Who of Women of the Century" by the Cambridge International Biographical Center, UK, etc. Mr. Zhou Guangren's life, like her name, is the life of "Guangshi Benevolence", which will be recorded in the annals of the development of Chinese piano art. Her dedication to serving the country and the party in the form of music education was one of the indispensable forces in the democratic revolutionary movement at that time, and she is also worthy of admiration.

3.3 A representative who lives overseas, cares about the motherland, and takes the promotion of Chinese piano music as his own responsibility: Li Xianmin

Li Xianmin is an outstanding representative of Chinese female pianists who lived overseas before and after the Agrarian Revolution, were concerned about the motherland, and took the promotion of Chinese piano music as their own responsibility. The development of Chinese piano music culture during this period was mainly professional piano education in schools. With the establishment of the National Shanghai Conservatory, professional music education across the country has also begun to develop, some colleges and universities have set up music departments or subjects, piano as the main course in music education has gradually been given an increasing importance and value, so many piano players are trained many and piano composers are cultivated in the future.

Li Xianmin, the first female pianist to promote Chinese piano music overseas, is the wife of the world-famous Russian-American composer Alexander Tcherepnin (1899-1977), and the first undergraduate graduate of Shanghai Conservatory in 1933. She is also the first pianist in China to reach the graduate level, and the first piano student trained in China. In 1934, she was admitted to the Gengzi Indemnity Scholarship and went to study at the Royal Conservatory of Belgium. She studied with Boris Zakharoff (1888-1943). In the early days, she mainly performed and was highly praised by the industry, and she visited more than a dozen countries including Britain, the United States, France and Germany during this period. After settling in the United States with her husband Zilpin in 1949, she taught at De Paul University in Chicago, where she spent 15 years. Her teaching is characterized by a unique insight into improving students' techniques and interpretation of musical styles. Later, she mainly lectured at universities and conservatories, participated in competitions, and tutored young students in competitions between Europe and the United States. Because of the new education received in her early years, although Li Xianmin mainly lived in the West, she has always been close to the motherland, and is full of infinite nostalgia and gratitude for the motherland, including: name, clothes, are all Chinese flavors, especially in the performance and teaching, always to introduce the works of Chinese composers as their own responsibility, to undertake the important task of promoting the exchange of Chinese and Western music culture, but also to many Chinese musicians, scholars, Music students support and help in their studies and lives, and strive to promote the exposure of these young Chinese musicians to the foreign cultures of Europe and the United States. Li Xianmin's high achievements, great contributions and profound influence in promoting Chinese piano music to the world are indispensable in the history of the development of Chinese piano art, witnessing the fraternity and greatness of Chinese female pianists, and are also one of the strong backing of China's democratic revolutionary movement, which is worth remembering.

Conclusion

To sum up, the social value made by the Chinese female pianists in the democratic revolutionary movement in the first half of the 20th century is mainly displayed in the following aspects:

(1) In the first half of the 20th century, Chinese female pianists with their firm conviction of devoting themselves to the revolutionary cause and their revolutionary enthusiasm and patriotic heart, have abandoned the favorable urban living conditions, traveled thousands of miles, and rushed to the forefront of the revolutionary struggle, and carried out active revolutionary propaganda activities with the unique appeal of music. Meanwhile they carried out active revolutionary propaganda activities with an excellent communist member of the Communist Party, always being active to fight for the liberation of women and awaken the most progressive intellectuals to participate in the democratic revolutionary movement at that time, which highlights the unique artistic charm of Chinese female pianists such as Zhiming.

(2) In the first half of the 20th century, most of the Chinese female pianists lived in high-ranking intellectual or famous families. They have enjoyed a rich material life foundation and received a unique school training mode, especially they enjoyed a convenient and rare environment for learning the piano and various opportunities to study and further study abroad, which made them become a generation of pianists and celebrities, and at the same time nourished their patriotic enthusiasm and feelings. In that special era, with the actions of "the rise and fall of the family and the country, the responsibility of the man" and "the rich help the salary", they also actively participated in the progressive social revolutionary activities, and became sponsors of the Chinese feminist movement and revolutionary movement, such as Shi Fengzhu and Wang Ruixian.

(3) In the first half of the 20th century, Chinese female pianists, influenced by their family environments since childhood, not only showed extremely high musical talent, also they regarded the piano as life. although the living conditions were superior, they were willing to study and practice hard for the obsessed piano, and went through unimaginable hardship for ordinary people. Whether born abroad or at home, with a grateful heart for the motherland, they are willing to dedicate their youth, blood, and even their lifelong energy to the piano cause of the motherland, and they cultivated a large number of piano talents for the motherland. Although their support was in a hidden form, their hearts were close to the front of the revolutionary struggle, and they continuously provided a steady stream of outstanding talents for the democratic revolutionary movement at that time, whose names worthy of our memory are Li Cuizhen, Zhou Guangren, and so on.

(4) In the first half of the 20th century, Chinese female pianists influenced by new education in the early years, were full of passion and strong interest in learning piano music culture originating from the West. In order to seek the true meaning of piano art and improve their piano performance skills and teaching standards as soon as possible, many Chinese female pianists chose to study abroad for various reasons. though they lived in the West in their old age, they have always been close to the motherland, and are filled with infinite nostalgia and gratitude for the motherland. they took the duty of introducing the works of Chinese composers as their own responsibility in their performance and teaching, and undertook the important task of promoting the exchange of music and culture between China and the West, giving support and help to many Chinese musicians, scholars and music students studying abroad, which greatly promoted the contact of these young Chinese musicians in Europe and the United States Exotic cultures and efforts such as: Li Xianmin, etc.

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